

FORMATION OF COGNITIVE VISUAL SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS SKILLS OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation

This article presents ideas and observations about the skills of future teachers in the formation of cognitive visual skills in future teachers in the context of the special course "Additional knowledge and skills in the formation of cognitive-visual".

Keywords: cognitive-visual views, additional knowledge, skills, future teachers, teacher skills, visual skills, innovative training, cognitive psychology.

In the research conducted by the world's leading higher educational institutions and scientific centers on innovative training of future specialists, implementation of modern education, special attention is paid to the introduction of the requirements of international educational standards, the criteria for the professional skills of future teachers, the problems of creating an innovative educational environment. In this regard, scientific research aimed at expanding the composition of pedagogical competence of young teachers on the basis of such indicators as motivational, cognitive, operational, reflexive and self-assessment of the successful use of modern information and pedagogical technologies in the educational process plays an important role.

The pedagogical process is a complex systemic phenomenon. The high importance of the pedagogical process is associated with the cultural, historical and social significance of the process of personal maturation. In this regard, it is very important to understand the main specific features of the pedagogical process, to know what tools are needed for its most effective flow.

Many local and foreign specialists, pedagogical scientists, psychologists are studying this problem. Cognitive psychology is one of the most popular scientific areas of foreign psychology. Translated into Russian, the term "cognitive" means cognitive. This

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area of research was formed mainly in the 1960s, and the results of the first stage of its development were summarized in the monograph "Cognitive Psychology" by V. Neisser, published in 1967, which gave the name to a new direction in psychological thought. R. Solso, in his later book of the same name, writes that cognitive psychology studies how people perceive information about the world, how this information is represented by a person, how it is stored in memory and transformed into knowledge, and how this knowledge affects our attention and behavior. Thus, almost all cognitive processes are covered - from sensations to perception, pattern recognition, memory, concept formation, thinking, imagination.

The main directions of cognitive psychology, which have been widespread in many countries for several decades, usually include research on the problems of the developmental psychology of cognitive structures, the psychology of language and speech, and the development of cognitive theories. Thus, cognitive psychology is based on the idea of a person as a system that is engaged in the search for information about objects and phenomena in the surrounding world, as well as the processing and storage of incoming information. At the same time, individual cognitive processes ensure the implementation of various stages of information processing.

The concept of cognitive-visual activity entered the field of education as a result of scientific research by pedagogical psychologists. From a psychological point of view, the term "cognitive-visual activity" refers to the ability of a person to mentally perceive and process external information, how a specialist behaves in unexpected situations, how to take a new path in relationships with colleagues, how to perform ambiguous tasks, how to use information full of contradictions, and how to have a plan of action in consistently developing and complex processes.

Cognitive-visual activity is a direction in psychology, according to which individuals not only mechanically affect external events or internal factors, but also use the power of reason for this. Its theoretical approach is to understand how thinking is organized, how incoming information is processed, and how it is organized to make decisions or perform everyday tasks.

Cognitive-visual aids are related to cognition, thinking in one way or another, the mind and functions of the brain, the ability to receive input knowledge and information, to form concepts and to work with them.

Cognitive activity is understood as a person's ability to process thoughts. It is "the ability of a person to perform various mental actions that are closely related to learning and problem solving. For example, verbal, spatial, psychomotor and processing speed skills". Cognition mainly refers to things like memory, speech and the ability to learn new information. This is the brain's ability to learn new skills and develop personal ideas and beliefs about the world in the areas mentioned above, usually in early childhood. Aging and disease can affect cognitive activity, causing memory loss and problems thinking of the right words when speaking or writing. Multiple sclerosis, for example, can eventually lead to memory loss, difficulty understanding new concepts or information, and decreased verbal fluency.

People are usually born with a high capacity for cognitive activity, so almost everyone has the ability to learn or remember. Intelligence is tested with IQ tests and others, although there are problems with their accuracy and completeness. In such tests, people may be asked a series of questions or complete tasks, each of which measures cognitive abilities such as attention, memory, awareness, problem-solving, motor skills, analytical skills, or other similar concepts. Research is concerned with human cognitive activity, and cognitivism is based on the idea that it is a mental activity, not a behavior.

Cognitive tools are in one way or another related to cognition, thinking, consciousness and the functions of the brain, the acquisition of input knowledge and information, the formation of concepts, and their operation. Cognitive activity is studied by psychologists and educators from various angles, but any research is considered as part of the general problem of education and development. All such efforts are aimed at improving the educational process.

Cognitive functions, also called cognitive skills, are brain-based skills necessary for acquiring knowledge, manipulating information, and reasoning. They are more related to the mechanisms of learning, remembering, problem-solving, and paying attention than to the knowledge of people. Cognitive skills or functions cover the domains of perception, attention, memory, learning, decision-making, and language development. The problem of forming students' cognitive activity in the learning process is one of the most important issues in modern pedagogical science, because improving the quality of education, motivating students to achieve academic and

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creative results largely depends on its solution. The solution to such problems is considered to be further improving the potential of pedagogical personnel, expanding their capabilities, and becoming stronger both mentally and physically. The spiritual maturity of a teacher, a strong self-confident character, the ability to find a solution to any problem and solve it, is becoming a requirement of today. Summarizing these, we can say that we call cognitive-visual skills, and it is necessary to implement and develop this process in the activities of teachers. A lot of pedagogical and psychological work has been carried out to develop the cognitive-visual characteristics of teachers, and the fact that it has been studied by many scientists shows how important it is.

In conclusion, it can be said that the pedagogical process is a developing interaction between teachers and educators, aimed at achieving a certain goal and leading to a pre-planned change in the situation, changing the characteristics and qualities of the teacher. In other words, the pedagogical process is the process of assimilation of social experience into personal qualities. This process requires enormous knowledge, experience, and skills from the teacher. The same applies to cognitive-visual skills. Since it is necessary for a teacher to assess the situation in advance, study problems comprehensively, organize the flow of information in his mind, and achieve commonality in his thoughts and actions, the development and study of cognitive-visual skills remains relevant.

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